

HOW DOES PERCEPTION OF PROFIT OR LOSS AFFECT AN INDIVIDUAL'S INVESTMENT DECISION? A CASE STUDY IN VIETNAM

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Abstract

Recently, although behavioral finance is one of the most interesting topics, there is still a lack of empirical research in Vietnam. This study aims to analyze the influence of feelings after winning or losing on individual investment decisions. The research is practiced based on prospect theory and overconfidence. The experiment was conducted with 50 students of diverse disciplines, ages, and spending levels. They participate in the game of drawing a ball with 12 rounds. They have a chance to win 2.5 times the bet amount or lose nothing at each round. The Mann-Whitney test of two independent samples was employed to test the hypotheses. The results support the prospect theory that individuals feel more dissatisfied when they lose than they are satisfied when they win. This conclusion is supported by different genders, disciplines, and spending levels. However, when making new investment decisions, women are more affected by the previous results (winning or losing) than men. Furthermore, participants tend to invest more after each losing round. Thus, investors should cultivate financial knowledge and minimize personal emotions when making investment decisions to avoid wrong behaviors.

Keywords: Behavioral Finance, Prospect Theory, Perception, Individual's Investment, Experimental Research.

1. INTRODUCTION

Formal financial modeling seeks to understand financial markets using models in which rational investors possess all the necessary information to make sound decisions in the investment process. It is the crucial condition of the efficient market hypothesis. However, many studies show that investors do not always act rationally. According to Nofsinger (2001), the financial sector has evolved over the past few decades based on decisions that people make rational decisions and that they are not biased about their future predictions. Individual investment behavior can be defined as an investor's sequence of actions in response to market-related external environmental stimuli and investor internal factors. Behavioral finance has sought to explain the aspects of human behavior that influence investment decisions, even for professional investors (Kahneman and Tversky, 2013). Tozetti (2011) asserts that behavioral finance is used to justify irrational phenomena occurring in financial decision-making. It focuses on the evidence that people are not all alike when it comes to making investment decisions. Investment decisions are influenced not only by the theories of normative finance but also by other factors. One of them is the cognitive trends that affect the psychology of investors, thereby affecting their investment decisions. Can an individual investing in the

market always be able to make a reasonable investment decision? It is known that even though an individual has rational investment intentions, emotions always influence the decision-making process. It brings up the question of how people perceive and feel profits or losses affect future investment decisions. Individuals may make a bad decision regarding their investments because their mindset is influenced by past losses or profits. In order to provide more evidence on the impact of personal feelings on investment decisions, a study on the effect of perceived loss or profit on investment decisions should be conducted in Vietnam.

2. LITERATURE AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Literature Review

Orthodox financial theory has explained financial markets using a paradigm in which market participants are rational individuals. First, when these people receive new information, they update their beliefs correctly. Then, they make choices to maximize the theoretically expected utility. This tradition seems simple and would be satisfied if its predictions were confirmed in reality. Regrettably, after many years of research, it has become clear that the basic facts about the stock market, average earnings, and individual buying behavior are not easy to understand in the traditional theory. Behavioral finance is a new approach to financial markets: explaining investor theoretical models with emotional developments and how they influence investment decisions as a solution to the difficulties facing the mainstream financial markets. This theory suggests that some financial phenomena can be better understood using samples in which investors are not rational. More specifically, behavioral finance theory analyzes what happens when we loosen one or both of the pillars that underpin individual rationality. In some behavioral finance models, market participants have failed to update their beliefs correctly. In other cases, even though investors correctly applied Bayes' law (calculating the probability of a random event A, given that related event B has occurred), they seem to have made choices by questionable standards. One of the greatest successes of behavioral finance is the set of scholarly arguments that show that in an economy where rational and emotional investors interact with each other. The irrationality can have an important and lasting effect on prices.

The models proposed by behavioral finance theory will be correct if one of the following three basic conditions exists in the market: irrational behavior, systematic irrational behavior, and limit the possibility of arbitrage in the financial markets. If all three exist, behavioral finance theory predicts that mispricing is not only present but very significant (large or severe) and persistent (Tversky and Kahneman, 2013). Barberis and Thaler (2002) pointed out irrational behaviors including overconfidence, representativeness heuristic, loss aversion, heuristics, anchoring, Mental accounts, herb behavior...

Besides, an important theory of behavioral finance is prospect theory. Kahneman and Tversky (1979) introduced the idea of prospect theory. This theory holds that people value gains and losses differently and decisions are based on seeing gains rather than losses. So if a person is given two equal options, one expressed in terms of profit and one expressed in terms of loss, everyone will choose the first choice - even if they achieve the same profit. According to prospect theory, losses have more influence on investor sentiment than comparable gains. For

example, according to traditional theories, the utility that a "rational" investor gains from receiving \$50 is equivalent to gaining \$100 and then losing \$50. In both situations, the result is a net profit of \$50. Although players still end up getting \$50 in both cases, most people would rather get \$50 than gain \$100 and lose \$50. The chances of tossing a coin are equal in both cases, but people choose to play the game to save their losses, even if this game can bring a larger profit. This shows the tendency of people to consider the ability to cover a loss more important than the ability to make a larger profit.

Prospect theory also leads to an asymmetric value function shape, which is concave on the profit side and convex on the loss side and has a twist at the origin. This point is called the reference point. Figure 1 shows the utility function according to prospect theory. The value function has a steeper slope for values below the reference point, which means values below the reference point, investors are more risk-seeking. At the same time, they are willing to make riskier investments to move above the reference point. Meanwhile, for value levels above the reference point, the value function has a decreasing slope, investors are afraid of losses. Investors like risk for losses while being risk averse to gains.

Fig.1 The utility function according to prospect theory

Besides, the account allocation effect is a type of behavioral trend where investors tend to stay in a losing position for a long time and liquidate a winning position very soon. This tendency stems from the irrational calculations of investors, who tend to separate decisions into virtual accounts of their imagination that should be put together, then take maximum benefits from each account. Therefore, investors often make mistakes in making decisions that they think are reasonable. These unreasonable calculations can lead to account allocation effects in investors' investments. According to research by Hirshleifer (2001), people tend to want their good decisions to be acknowledged immediately, but they are slow to accept their bad decisions. They conclude that the investor's professionalism in investing can reduce the account allocation effect. In the US, Dhar and Zhu (2002) studied the effect of demographics such as income and job type on the account allocation effect. They conclude that professional investors exhibit a

lower tendency to this behavior (about 10-20% smaller than other investors). In addition, they also proved that investors who trade frequently also tend to reduce the account allocation effect.

On the other hand, rational investors only execute trades if the expected return exceeds the transaction costs. However, overconfident investors overestimate the accuracy of their information and the expected return of a trade, so they will execute the trade even though the expected net profit is not positive. Therefore, because men are more overconfident than women, they will trade more but perform worse than women. Some studies also suggest that women are less confident about their investment choices than men (Barber and Odean, 2001; Yao and Hanna, 2005; Fernandes et al., 2017). They concluded that women invest more conservatively (Yao and Hanna, 2005) and are more risk averse (Agnew, 2006) than men. According to Eckel and Grossman (2008), if women are more risk sensitive than men, it will reflect all aspects of decision making, including career decisions and investment and product purchase decisions.

In addition, Barber and Odean (2001) surveyed 35,000 households for six years. The results show that men are generally more confident and invest more often than women. Men do not only invest at the wrong time but invest more than women. The results of the study show that men invest 45% more than women, and surprisingly, single men invest 67% more than single women. However, the more they invest, the worse investment decisions they make. Investment costs have reduced net profit a year by 2.65% for men while this figure is only 1.72% for women.

Through the comprehensive review of prior studies related to the research topic, many of them employed non-parametric testing methods to analyze the influence of perceived profit or loss on investment decisions. It is important to address that the proposed research model in this study expands the current literature in three aspects: (a) whether dissatisfaction after losing is more than satisfaction after winning, (b) whether risk aversion decrease after winning or losing, (c) whether dissatisfaction after losing or satisfaction after winning effects next investment decisions.

2.2. Hypotheses Development

Personal feelings after profit or loss

Kahneman and Tversky (2013) have shown that people feel more distressed by potential losses than happy by equivalent gains - individuals are the losers. Some economists have concluded that investors view the loss of \$1 as twice as painful as the joy of gaining \$1. Furthermore, people will react differently to similar situations depending on the profit or loss context. Therefore, this study conducted the first hypothesis test:

H1: Dissatisfaction after loss is more than satisfaction after gain.

Personal risk aversion

Human behavior depends on the nature of the prospect, human behavior sometimes exhibits risk aversion (risk avoidance) and sometimes risk preference (risk seeking). People make investment choices based on their expectations of profit or loss (Kahneman and Tversky, 2013).

People fear losses because losses affect their emotions more strongly than gains. After a loss of investment, they tend to invest more next time – this will demonstrate dissatisfaction after a loss leading to a reduction in personal risk aversion. Therefore, this study proposed the following hypothesis:

H2: Dissatisfaction after a loss leads to a decrease in individual risk aversion

The influence of past profits and losses on gender

According to behavioral finance theory, some studies suggest that women are less confident about their investment choices and invest less money than men (Barber and Odean, 2001). Therefore, this study poses the final hypothesis:

H3: Women are more influenced than men for future investment decisions due to past profits or losses.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Sample Selection

The applied experimental study builds on previous studies (Tozetti, 2011; Fernandes et al., 2017) with the participation of 50 students. The experiment was performed by drawing one of three balls. Each ball represents a color and is drawn at random by another student who not participating in the experiment to ensure the objectivity of the results.

Participating students receive an answer sheet to their bets for each of the twelve rounds. In each round, the probability of winning is 1/3 to get 2.5 times the bet amount, and the probability of losing is 2/3 to get nothing back. Participants choose a value from 1,000 to 10,000 VND to bet and check the number for each round on the answer sheet. A student wins the lottery if the color of the ball drawn matches the color on that student's answer sheet. The balls are equally distributed and can be yellow, green, or red. At the end of each round, students must choose one of four states that represent their emotions after a profit or loss result.

To analyze the data, we set the number for each emotional state as close to the selected number as 1, the more satisfied the students. On the other hand, the closer to the selected number of 4, the more dissatisfied students. Therefore, we can set 2.5 as the level of indifference, where students are neither satisfied nor disgruntled. After this process, a new round is started and the student has another 10,000 coins to bet and so on up to twelve rounds.

3.2. Estimation Method

The non-parametric test is a test that requires little hypothesis about the distribution of the data. Non-parametric tests are most useful in cases where it is not possible to use parametric tests. We can determine significance levels for the non-parametric test regardless of the sample distribution because the non-parametric test is based on the rank of the data. The Mann-Whitney test of two independent samples is used to test hypotheses about two independent variables derived from two populations with dissimilar distributions. Therefore, to test the

difference between satisfaction after a gain and dissatisfaction after a loss, this study uses the Mann–Whitney test. The test value is calculated according to the following formula:

$$U = n_1 n_2 + \frac{n_2(n_2+1)}{2} - \sum_{i=n_1+1}^{n_2} R_i \quad (1)$$

$$Z = \frac{(U - \frac{n_1 n_2}{2})}{\sqrt{\frac{n_1 n_2 (n_1 + n_2 + 1)}{12}}} \quad (2)$$

Where: n_1 is the number of observations in group 1, n_2 is the number of observations in group 2, R_i is the rank of observations in group 2.

The above value is used to test the hypothesis pair:

$$\begin{cases} H_0: a=b \\ H_1: a < b \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The values of a and b are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Research Hypothesis Pairs

Hypothesis	Values of a and b respectively
H1: Dissatisfaction after loss is more than satisfaction after gain.	a is dissatisfaction after a loss. b is the satisfaction after profit.
H2: Dissatisfaction after a loss leads to a decrease in individual risk aversion	a is the amount individuals continue to invest after winning b is the amount individuals continue to invest after losing.
H3: Women are more influenced than men for future investment decisions due to past profits or losses.	a is the total amount of female investment. b is the total amount of male investment.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Empirical Results

Table 2 shows the results of descriptive statistics on the factors of gender, major and expenditure of students participating in the experiment.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics on gender and expenditure of interviewees

Variable	Value	Gender				Total	
		Male		Female		Number of observations	Proportion (%)
		Number of observations	Proportion (%)	Number of observations	Proportion (%)		
Age	18	11	22	5	10	16	32
	19	7	14	6	12	13	26
	20	5	10	8	16	13	26
	21	1	2	1	2	2	4
	22	1	2	5	10	6	12
	Total	25	50	25	50	50	100
Expenditure (Million VND/month)	1-1.5	8	16	10	20	18	36
	2-3	12	24	12	24	24	48
	4-5	5	10	3	6	8	16
	Total	25	50	25	50	50	100
	Majors	Economics	-	-	-	-	15
Education	-	-	-	-	4	8	
Law	-	-	-	-	2	4	
Technology	-	-	-	-	4	8	
Information & Communications Technology	-	-	-	-	4	8	
Political Science	-	-	-	-	3	6	
Natural Resources and Environment	-	-	-	-	2	4	
Fisheries	-	-	-	-	1	2	
Social Sciences & Humanities	-	-	-	-	3	6	
Agriculture & Applied Biology	-	-	-	-	12	24	
Total	-	-	-	-	50	100	

4.2 Personal feelings after profit or loss

Table 3 shows the results of testing the hypothesis that dissatisfaction after a loss is greater than satisfaction after a gain.

Table 3: Test results of hypothesis 1

Hypothesis	Z	Z _α (α=1%)	Conclusion
(1.1) Dissatisfaction after loss and satisfaction after a gain in the study sample are the same	-8.414	2.33	Reject H ₀
(1.2) Dissatisfaction after a loss and satisfaction after a gain for women are the same	-6.073	2.33	Reject H ₀
(1.3) Dissatisfaction after a loss and satisfaction after a gain for men are the same	-5.740	2.33	Reject H ₀
(1.4) Dissatisfaction after a loss and satisfaction after a gain of the economic group are the same	-4.302	2.33	Reject H ₀
(1.5) Dissatisfaction after a loss and satisfaction after a gain of the social group are the same	-7.177	2.33	Reject H ₀
(1.6) Dissatisfaction after a loss and satisfaction after a gain in the high spending group are the same	-4.481	2.33	Reject H ₀
(1.7) Dissatisfaction after a loss and satisfaction after a gain in the low spending group are the same	-7.072	2.33	Reject H ₀

With hypothesis (1.1) in Table 3, $|Z| = 8,414 > Z_{0.01} = 2.33$, so the null hypothesis can be rejected at 1% significance level. We can conclude that the dissatisfaction experienced by the individual in the study from losing is greater than the satisfaction from making a profit. This result is consistent with that of Kahneman and Tversky (2013), Fernandes et al. (2017). However, to confirm this hypothesis more objectively, the study has conducted a test with each factor and reviewed the data analyzed in the study.

Firstly, it can be concluded that both men and women feel more dissatisfied after losing than satisfied after gaining profit, according to the results of hypothesis testing (1.2) and (1.3) in Table 3. In addition, the study estimates the perceived level of individuals after losses and after profits through the data analyzed in the study. Figure 2 presents the results regarding the perception of gender after winning and losing. Dissatisfaction after losing is greater than satisfaction after winning, even when the profit is 2.5 times the value of the loss. Although the study found that both men and women showed more dissatisfaction after a loss than satisfaction after a profit, when considered individually, both men and women seem to feel close to 2.5 after winning. This shows that both men and women are not interested in investment results when they have profits, whereas, after losses, women are more dissatisfied than men.

Fig. 2 Perceived value after winning or losing by gender

Next, the results of hypothesis testing (1.4) and (1.5) show that students in both economic and social groups feel more dissatisfied after losing than satisfied after winning a round. In addition, Figure 3 presents the results related to the cognitive level after winning and losing the two groups of disciplines. Accordingly, when considering the average value of each industry, after winning, the economic group showed more interest in profit than the social group. At the same time, after losing, the economic group also showed more dissatisfaction than the social group. It is possible that economic students mostly have a deeper understanding of the investment sector, so they are more sensitive than individuals in other groups.

Fig. 3 Feelings after winning or losing by majors expenditure

Fig. 4 Feelings after winning or losing by expenditure

Finally, the conclusion to reject the hypothesis (1.6) and (1.7) in Table 3 shows that the dissatisfaction after a loss is greater than the satisfaction after gaining a profit occurs in both high and low spending groups. Figure 4 presents the results related to the cognitive level after winning and losing the two spending groups. It can be determined in Figure 4 that dissatisfaction after losing is higher than satisfaction after winning in both high and low spending groups. However, when considering each case separately, the group with a low spending level tends to be more interested and satisfied than the group with a high spending level after winning. At the same time, after losing, the low spending group also showed less dissatisfaction than the high spending group.

4.3 Personal risk aversion

Table 4 presents the results of testing hypothesis about dissatisfaction after a loss leads to a decrease in individual risk aversion.

Table 4: Test results of hypothesis 2

Hypothesis	Z	Z _α (α=1%)	Conclusion
(2.1) The amount invested after winning is equal to the amount invested after losing	-3.697	2.33	Reject H ₀
(2.2) The amount invested by the male after winning is equal to the amount invested after losing	-2.999	2.33	Reject H ₀
(2.3) The amount invested by the female after winning is equal to the amount invested after losing	-2.456	2.33	Reject H ₀

With the hypothesis (2.1) in Table 4, $|Z|=3,697 > Z_{0.01}=2.33$ shows that the null hypothesis is rejected at 1% significance level. It can be concluded that the amount invested after winning is less than the amount invested after losing. This result proves that dissatisfaction after a loss leads to a decrease in the risk aversion of individuals, and they want to invest more money. To confirm this hypothesis more objectively, the study conducted a test with each factor and examined the data analyzed in the sample.

The results of hypothesis testing (2.2) and (2.3) in Table 4 demonstrate that dissatisfaction after a loss leads to a reduction in individual risk aversion of both men and women. The results show that when an investment tends to yield a profit, they prefer to hold on to the current profit rather than try to continue investing to earn more profits in the future. But on the contrary, when the investment is at risk of loss, they try to continue investing in the hope of receiving profits in the future, even if the risk of loss is high. It can be explained by psychological deviation due to fear of losing. Loss Aversion Bias is a psychological state in which people are afraid of loss, which has a greater psychological impact than the effect of the same gain. Fear of losing is also gradually becoming popular with investors in the market.

In addition, when conducting experiments through twelve rounds. The study found that risk aversion started to decrease towards the end of the rounds and individuals increased their investment amount as the experiment neared the end. The increase in the investment amount is similar for both men and women. But men tend to increase investment amounts more than women. This result is similar to the results of Barberis and Thaler (2002). Faint risk aversion leads to a greater sensitivity to loss than to gain, and a tendency to evaluate outcomes frequently. The behavior of investors is sometimes said to be short-sighted, and lack vision. Because they only see things from one side, they often overlook a lot of things that can happen, so all investors point to plan for a specific period only (Bodie et al., 2000). The two assumptions of myopic risk aversion are tested empirically. First, risk-averse investors will be willing to take risks if they evaluate their investments less often. Second, if the results increase enough to limit the loss, the investor will accept more risk. Risk aversion indicates that people tend to be more sensitive to a decrease in profit gain than to an increase. Figure 5 shows the average bet amount for each round.

Fig. 5 Average bet per round

Figure 6 shows the average investment amount of individuals after winning and after losing by age. We can see the average investment amount of individuals of different ages. The amount invested after losing at all ages is more than the investment amount after winning. Besides, the

amount of investment after losing decreases with each age. The lower the investment amount after losing, the more risk aversion it has. In this study, it can be observed that with increasing age, risk aversion increases. At that time, individuals of older ages will invest less after losing. According to previous behavioral finance research by Dhar and Zhu (2006), older investors often have weaker account allocation effects than younger investors. Furthermore, the older the person, the more aversion to loss (Mrkva et al., 2020). Young people often have bold thinking and often apply innovative methods in their investment analysis. As a result, they are often more invested and riskier (Goetzmann and Kumar, 2008). In addition, older investors have lower levels of overconfidence than younger investors. Therefore, over time, the conservatism of age increases as they tend to slow down in investment decisions (Barber and Odean, 2001).

Fig. 6 The average investment amount of individuals after winning and after losing by age

Figure 7 shows the average investment amount after winning and losing by the spending group. The study conducted statistics and data analysis for three spending groups, including group 1 (1-1.5 million VND), group 2 (2-2.5 million VND), and group 3 (4- 5 million). Accordingly, the average investment amount after losing in all three spending groups is higher than the average investment amount after winning. This result strengthens the conclusion that risk aversion decreases in all three spending groups because after losing in all three groups, there is a tendency to invest more. Besides, when considering different spending groups, we also find that group 1 (lowest spending) has the most investment amount even after winning or losing. Group 3 (highest spend) has the lowest average investment amount even after winning or losing. Thus, the average amount of investment of individuals across groups decreases with the level of expenditure. The higher the level of spending, the less the investment, even after winning or losing. It proves that the level of risk aversion increases with more spending. The result of the study on expenditure is consistent with the statement of Gächter et al. (2010), investors' fear of loss increases with age, wealth, and spending.

Fig. 7 The average investment amount after winning and losing by spending group

Fig. 8 The average investment amount after winning and losing by majors

Figure 8 shows that the amount invested after losing is more than after winning in both industry groups. However, investors in the economic group often invest more immediately after winning or after losing than other industry groups. This result can be explained by the account allocation effect. Individuals are willing to execute orders for small profits but delay in executing stop-loss orders when small (or possibly large) losses appear. Hirshleifer (2001) pointed out that investor professionalism in investing can reduce the account allocation effect. Economic students will have more knowledge about statistical probability and investment than students studying other disciplines. Thus, economic students will be less affected by the account allocation effect than other majors.

4.4 The influence of past profits and losses on gender

Table 5 presents the results of testing hypothesis about the influence of past profits and losses on gender.

Table 5: Test results of hypothesis 3

Hypothesis	Z	Z _α (α=5%)	Conclusion
(3.1) The total investment of the female is equal to the total investment of the male	-3.048	1.65	Reject H ₀
(3.2) The total investment amount after winning by women is equal to the total investment amount after winning by men	-2.019	1.65	Reject H ₀
(3.3) The total investment amount after loss of the female is equal to the total investment amount after the loss of the male	-2.389	1.65	Reject H ₀

With the hypothesis (3.1) in Table 5, the test results $|Z|=3.048 > Z_{0.05}=1.65$, reject the null hypothesis, that the total investment of women is less than the total investment of men whether win or lose after 12 rounds, at a 5% statistical significance level. Similarly, hypotheses (3.2) and (3.3) are rejected at a 5% significance level, it can be concluded that the amount of investment of women in the next round is less than that of men when they win or lose in the

previous round. As a result, women are more influenced than men by investment decisions due to past profits or losses. This is understandable when most women do not like taking risks. This result is consistent with some studies on gender influence in investment decisions as Yao and Hanna (2005), Agnew (2006), and Fernandes et al. (2017). Men are more overconfident than women, they will trade more. However, the results are worse than for women. In general, after winning or losing, the investment level of women is lower than that of men.

On the other hand, Figure 9 presents the average bets of the respondents for the entire experiment. This figure is the bet level both after a profit and after a loss. On average, individuals invest nearly 63% value of the previous round. While men invest about 70%, women invest 54% value of the previous round. Therefore, men show less risk-averse behavior than women. Men have more investment behavior after profit or loss, women show more stable behavior than men. This result is evidence that women are more affected by previous losses or gains than men.

Fig. 9 Average investment by men and women

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study analyzes the influence of perceived profit or loss on an individual's investment decision. The ball-drawing experiment was conducted with 50 students aged between 18-22 years old in various majors at the university. Participating students receive an answer sheet to record their bets for each of the twelve rounds. At the end of each round, students must choose one of four states that represent their emotions after a profit or a loss. The results have demonstrated that individuals feel more dissatisfied after a loss than satisfied after gaining a profit. Furthermore, participants' dissatisfaction after a loss leads to a reduction in personal risk aversion, stimulating them to invest more in the next round. The results are similar for each gender, discipline, and spending group. At the same time, risk aversion also increases with age and expenditure. Both genders act similarly when making investment decisions, but females

are more influenced than males on future investment decisions due to past profits or losses. In short, investors are very susceptible to behavioral and psychological factors.

Therefore, each investor needs to have a clear investment strategy to minimize the impact of personal feelings when making investment decisions. First, to avoid psychological distortions in the investment process, investors must control emotional factors. Second, basic rules need to be set and followed to overcome emotions of greed and fear. Third, individuals should supplement their knowledge of behavioral finance and apply that knowledge to investment decisions. Fourth, investors should consider their behavior and that of others when investing, thereby making a reasonable decision for themselves. Fifth, reinforce behaviors that positively affect investment performance and avoid wrong behavior. Finally, limiting emotions affects the decision-making process. Due to time, cost, and human resource limitations, this study only surveyed university students. The representativeness of the sample was not high. Therefore, future studies should be conducted on a more diverse sample to reflect more generally on the level of perceived influence on individual investment decisions.

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